

Online E-Campus Interview Training MOOC Framework for Graduates

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Abstract :

Currently, Academic MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) is widely recognized as a major step in disruptive innovations that is taking place in Higher Education sector today. Simulative MOOC is also adopted in corporations for staff or personnel trainings for cutting down training costs and time at Industry. Moreover, with E-HRM also partially disrupting orthodox HR Processes at Industry level, Online E-Campus Interviews have also become more immensely evident towards graduate hiring presently. Therefore, training job seeking graduates for achieving success in current online interviews in this regard too has also become a very paramount challenge for training & placement services cell of educational institutions. Therefore as a solution, this paper attempts to construct a very basic simulative MOOC prototype framework with a very comprehensive online interview training contents which we feel shall benefit all the stakeholders involved. Accordingly, possible sample contents, materials and syllabus are formulated for developing into full-fledged online e-training & learning platform for further studies.

Keywords: E-Campus Interview Training, MOOC Training for Online Interviews, Online Interview Training, Skill Development Training, Vocational MOOC

I. Introduction :

Present days in industry recruitment or selection processes is the foreplay of E-HRM in the limelight. E-HRM refers to widespread usage & application of electronic methodologies, digital platforms plus cutting edge technologies plus World Wide Web internet to social media in candidate recruitment process. E-HRM is significantly influencing campus recruitment processes at business schools presently and is expected to be recognized as a

standard single running procedure or format to be followed in future by campus recruiters with rapid development in Automation, Robotics, Artificial Intelligence Technology as well as Internet of Things (IoT) or any other revolutions in digital world. This E-HRM powered process is identified as online e-campus interview/placement/recruitment at management institutions. Apparently, Industry in this regard is expecting the Training & Placement teams at business schools to train the students to confront or interface E-HRM process powered online e-campus interviews in the days coming to up-skill the campus student talent pool for their career prospects in Industry. Therefore, this paper attempts to develop a Framework for Online E-Campus Interview training MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) towards job seeking students at campus and also for the benefit of industry. The framework along with its detailed required expected criteria will be presented before the stakeholders in this study.

II. Objectives of the Study :

The main objective of this paper is to develop a robust student e-placement training MOOC (Massive Online Open Course) blueprint for placement success at E-HRM powered Online E-campus interview. The aim under the framework here is to propose a digital platform where MOOC can be hosted as well as the online e-interview training contents uploaded into the MOOC. Secondary purpose of the study also seeks that framework constructed if brought into reality will serve as a basic level training extension of E-HRM Industry requirements at graduate education campuses. Final aim is that the study will focus on efforts made to bridge the gap between Industry and Academia.

III. Research Methodology :

The Information gathering process required to develop the sample framework was divided into a two-step process. Firstly, to construct the online e-training components expected in the MOOC framework Sample, direct interview method was utilized via field visits and telephonic conversations to gather information from industry recruiters on their expectations from fresh graduates in alignment to E-HRM. The technology used to interview or source the candidates were also discussed. Accordingly, these recruiters formed as a part of head hunters of NIRF (National Institute Ranking Framework India) ranked Top 10 Indian Business Schools. For the second set of data collection, select group of professors from Srinivas College of Computer & Information Sciences were consulted for the work-flow required for constructing the MOOC Server Platform in the framework. The gathered data in aforementioned methodology is then converted into modular table representation under relevant headings for understanding actual proposal determination and interpretations.

IV. Proposed MOOC Framework for Stakeholder Interpretations :

Based upon collected data and intended plan, the recommended MOOC framework for training students for online e-campus interview facing preparations is expected to be conceptualized as per below diagrams :

Table 1 : Basic proposed Component Architecture of expected Online E-Campus Interview Training MOOC :

Table 2 : Detailed IT Structure Segregation Build expected for the proposed MOOC

Table 3 : Detailed Segregation of Online E-Training Components expected for Inclusion in the MOOC Structure

<p>Online E-Training Components expected for Inclusion in the MOOC IT Structure</p>	<p>Sample Components</p>
<p>(a) Online E-Training Syllabus,</p>	<p>Detailed Unit-wise plan structure with Training Objectives, Purpose, Components, Training Pedagogy</p>
<p>(b) Online E-Training Plan</p>	<p>Session Wise Units with relevant topics, time hours, practical aspects, reference websites, links and so on</p>
<p>(c) Online E-Interview facing training simulations</p>	<p>Online Employability Test Studies, Simulated or Animated Group Discussion Video Studies,</p>

	Video Conference Interview sessions, Webinars and Video Panel Interviews, Essay Typing tests, Video Opinion Tests and so on
(d) Practice Materials	Huge Library of Simulated learning using audio-visual and electronic learning

As discussed in the tabular diagram 1 above, the primary proposal for constructing a robust Online E-Campus Interview Training Model can be categorised into (a) The Digital Platform where course will be hosted and (b) Actual Training Contents.

Table 2 and 3 details the complete expected construction build for the prototype framework. However, to realize this idea into reality for the benefit of placement success of students at online e-interviews, stakeholders are requested to develop interest for employing the required personnel, facility, key resources, capital and time as a project for bringing the portal into reality. The inventors would be happy for Patent Agreements and Knowledge expertise sharing. Interested Students could also take this idea up to develop into a full-fledged platform through start-up initiatives.

V. ABCD Listing of the proposed MOOC Framework :

The proposed Online E-Campus Interview training framework is evaluated through ABCD Analysis’s listing technique developed by Aithal et.al (2015).

(1) Advantages :

- The framework promotes the spirit of self-learning among students.
- The Model is advantageous for Industry to align their E-HRM Requirements.

(2) Benefits :

- The MOOC enables students to practice from home anytime/anywhere.
- The Framework is a Cash Cow Opportunity for Investors and Companies in product development work space.

(3) Constraints :

- Converting the Framework into working reality is challenge oriented owing to varying requirements of the market player or decision makers.
- Licensing and Patenting Constraints.

(4) Disadvantages :

- Inherently disadvantageous if the framework lacks the required feature as per changing industry trend in the prototype phase.

VI. Conclusion :

To summarize this study, we have formulated a sample draft Online E-Placement Training MOOC Framework for successful student placements at online e-campus interviews. The framework constructed by authors include (a) the digital platform where the MOOC is hosted (b) training contents designed based on information collected from Industry as per E-HRM alignment. Anyways in coming future, inventors of this framework hope this idea can be realized through converting the framework into an actual full-fledged platform for the e-interview training or practice of job seeking students in an E-HRM set-up of today. Inventors also welcome for any further feedback or suggestions from stakeholders interested in the idea to improve the draft or its contents subject to evaluative requirements.

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